

Response of rice genotypes to N fertilization under temperate conditions of Kashmir Valley

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SKAU5 formerly K39 is a medium-duration (133 d) rice cultivar that has been widely cultivated during the past 20 yr in the main belt of the Kashmir Valley. Reliance on a single variety could prove disastrous over the long term. Diversifying the varieties grown in the area needs to be considered, particularly with the recent introduction of rice-based double cropping systems. Further, there are indications that the N needs of rice are likely to be greater than the current recommendation of 80 kg N ha⁻¹.

We studied the response of five rice varieties to five levels of N in a split-plot design during 1991 and 1992 kharif (dry) seasons (May-September). The experimental site was 1650 m above sea level, 34.1 °N latitude and 74.9 °E longitude. The soil was silty clay loam in texture, with pH 6.8, 1.21% organic C, 13.7 and 16.2 kg available P ha⁻¹ (Olsen's method), 112 and 128 kg available K ha⁻¹ (ammonium acetate extraction method), 0.01 and 0.012% available N (alkaline permanganate

Yield and yield attributes of rice genotypes under different levels of N. Shalimar, Srinagar Kashmir, India. 1991 and 1992 kharif.

Treatment	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)		Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)		1000-grain weight (g)		Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Days to maturity	
	1991	1992	1991	1992	1991	1992	1991	1992	1991	1992
N level (kg ha ⁻¹)										
0	249	249	77	65	23.4	23.1	2.3	2.5	129	129
40	326	327	72	70	24.0	23.6	3.5	3.8	130	131
80	383	381	83	80	24.6	24.0	4.5	4.7	132	133
120	424	421	91	88	24.2	24.1	5.3	5.5	132	133
160	437	435	89	89	24.2	24.1	5.8	6.1	133	134
LSD (0.05)	13	9	5	4	0.5	0.2	0.2	0.3	1.9	2.0
Genotype										
SKAU5	363	361	79	78	23.9	23.8	4.3	4.5	133	134
SKAU11	362	361	82	80	24.1	23.7	4.2	4.4	133	134
SKAU23	362	360	81	78	24.2	23.8	4.2	4.4	126	127
SKAU27	367	365	81	79	24.1	23.9	4.2	4.5	132	132
SKAU30	365	366	81	79	24.1	23.9	4.3	4.6	132	133
LSD (0.05)	ns ^a	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	1.21	1.4

^ans = not significant.

method) during 1991 and 1992, respectively. Thirty-five-day-old seedlings were fertilized before transplanting with 19.8 kg P ha⁻¹, 16.6 kg K ha⁻¹, and half of the designated amount of N. The remaining N was applied in two equal splits at tillering and panicle initiation. Management practices were identical during both years.

Yield, yield components, and the nature of yield responses to N were similar over both years (see table). Rice grain yield increased with each increment of N up to 160 kg ha⁻¹, which registered the maximum yield of 5.8 t ha⁻¹ during 1991.

The optimum dose of N was 143 kg ha⁻¹, calculated from the pooled grain yield. Increase in grain yield occurred mainly through the contribution of panicles m⁻². Grains panicle increased consistently up to 120 kg N ha⁻¹ but 1,000-grain weight did not change with N rates.

Yield and yield attributes did not differ among the genotypes tested. However, SKAU23 matured 1 wk earlier than the others. N rates need to be increased from the current 80 kg to 140 kg ha⁻¹ for optimum yields. Cultivar SKAU23, which matures 1 wk earlier than SKAU5, can better fit in a double cropping system. ■

Grain quality

Enzyme isolation and regulation with lysine biosynthesis and degradation in developing seeds of rice

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The seeds of cereals are nutritionally deficient in certain essential amino acids. Aspartic acid serves as a common precursor of several amino acids, including lysine

(Lys), threonine (Thr), methionine (Met), and isoleucine (Ile). As yet, the aspartic acid pathway has not been studied in rice.

We are currently investigating the following enzymes in rice seeds: aspartate kinase (AK), the first enzyme of the pathway, and homoserine dehydrogenase (HSDH), which plays a major role in the biosynthesis of threonine, together with lysine ketoglutarate (LKR) and saccharopine dehydrogenase (SDH), both of which are involved in the catabolism of lysine.

All of the enzymes were extracted from the developing seeds, roots, and leaves of rice cultivar IAC165, and LKR and SDH only from the cotyledons and developing seeds of soybean in Tris and phosphate

buffers containing DTT, EDTA, PMSF, PVP, KCl, and glycerol. The enzymes were partially purified with an ammonium sulfate (0-60% saturation) precipitation step and desalted on Sephadex G25 or G50 columns. Enzyme activities were measured using the methods of Azevedo et al (1992a, 1992b) and Brochetto-Braga et al (1992).

All three stages presented AK and HSDH activities, with stage 2 showing higher levels of activity. Lys (5 mM) was the major inhibitor of AK activity, with inhibition varying from 30 to 90% among the stages tested (Table 1). Thr (5 mM) only slightly (4-12%) inhibited AK activity, and Lys or Thr did not inhibit HSDH (Table 1). Lys predominantly inhibited AK in rice as has been observed in all of the plant species